

FORMATION OF HARMONIOUSLY DEVELOPED INDIVIDUALS IN MODERN REALITIES: THE “GUBKIN’S” EXPERIENCE

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola zamonaviy sharoitlarda barkamol shaxsni shakllantirish xususiyatlarini o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan. Mualliflar Gubkin universitetining talabalarning bo‘sh vaqtini mazmunli tashkil etish tajribasi va uning neft va gaz sanoati uchun har tomonlama rivojlangan mutaxassislarini shakllantirishdagi rolini tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ma’naviy barkamol yoshlar, ta’lim va tarbiya, malaka oshirish, bo‘lajak mutaxassislar.

Abstract. This article is devoted to the investigation of the features of the formation of a harmoniously developed personality in modern realities. The authors analyze the experience of Gubkin University in organizing meaningful leisure time for students and its role in the formation of comprehensively developed specialists for the oil and gas industry.

Key words: spiritually mature youth, upbringing and education, skills development, future specialists.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена изучению особенностей формирования гармонично развитой личности в современных реалиях. Авторы анализируют опыт Губкинского университета в организации содержательного досуга студентов и его роли в формировании всесторонне развитых специалистов для нефтегазовой отрасли.

Ключевые слова: духовно зрелая молодежь, обучение и воспитание, развитие навыков, будущие специалисты.

From the first days of our country’s independence, education of a harmoniously developed generation, formation of comprehensively developed youth has become one of the priority focus areas of the government policy of Uzbekistan. A number of decrees and resolutions have been adopted with the aim of developing a harmoniously developed individual and these statutory acts create appropriate organizational and legal framework, which is constantly being improved. All adopted laws and statutory acts reflect one idea, which, according to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is to create the system required for the formation of a healthy generation, that is, physically healthy and spiritually mature youth, ensuring the protection of their rights and interests, as well as obtaining cutting-edge knowledge and profession, finding a worthy place in the life of society.

Moreover, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 focuses on the issues of high-quality education and cultivating personality of the younger generation. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted in his speech at the inauguration ceremony at a joint meeting of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis: “From now on, the focus of our

attention will be on the implementation of a fair social policy, ensuring quality education and upbringing as the most essential factor in the human capital development”.

In any country an efficient solution to the problem of cultivating personality of a harmoniously developed generation depends on many factors, among which the main ones are the availability of professional and higher education, a developed healthcare system, spiritual and moral activities, organization of meaningful leisure, creation of conditions for physical education and sports, a high level of development and implementation of information and communication technologies.

Undoubtedly, if every young person has the opportunity to demonstrate their talent and find application for it, to succeed in their profession, the quality of life will improve as a result. At the same time, the mission of the state is to create conditions for achieving success and realizing the potential of an individual’s talent within the framework of his professional activities.

At the same time, the mission of the government is to create conditions for achieving success and realizing the potential of an individual’s talent within the framework of his professional activities. These goals have become crucially important and are considered as strategic, national objectives in terms of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2021 №PD-6309 “On further support for gifted youth studying and engaged in research activities in higher educational institutions of the republic”. This Decree has become a motivational drive for students for constant self-development and being engaged in research activities, to reveal their talents and develop creative abilities, further support for educated and talented students, as well as the platform for the professional development of promising specialists.

The Branch of Russian State University of Oil and Gas (National Research University) named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent, along with the academic process, much focus is placed to the efficient organization of meaningful leisure time for students, their wide involvement in the research, social activities and sports. In particular, many students of the Branch are the members of the Student Scientific Union, a public organization that unites students participating in research, design, and creative activities. The activities of the Student Scientific Union are aimed at developing creative abilities, identifying and supporting talented youth, as well as shaping the personnel potential that is best prepared for research activities. With the active participation of this Union, the Branch annually hosts student scientific conferences “Oil and Gas” aimed at identifying innovative ideas and developments of young people for the development of the oil and gas industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In addition, in the Branch students may be engaged in various research and subject-oriented students teams, such as “Young Technicians”, “Young Field Engineer”, “Geophysicist”, “Free Radicals”, “Interpretation of Geological and Geophysical Data”, “I-practice club”, which goal is to develop the professional and general cultural competencies of students and improve personal qualities. Participation in these student teams develops students’ cognitive skills that encourage them to master new knowledge and develop professional and general cultural competencies, develop the skills of self-study in research, as well as the skills students need to develop professional competence and personal growth.

In order to raise the interest of students in research activities and development of their professional competencies, the Branch practices the experience of attracting gifted students to work as academic assistants in their free time. This practice has a number of advantages. Firstly, such performance contributes to the acquisition of new knowledge and real experience. In addition,

according to the students themselves, combining study with work is a good opportunity to learn what it is like to work in an educational institution, as well as a chance to approve themselves. And some of these students intend to connect their future professional careers with the research and academic activities.

Particular attention is paid to the physical development of students, since under modern conditions study and sports are the most significant means of educating a comprehensively developed person, harmoniously combining spiritual wealth, moral purity and physical perfection. There are various sports sections in the Branch, and students honorably defend the honorary title of “Gubkins” at sports competitions held at the interuniversity and republican levels.

Sports competitions that promote team spirit, unity, and also require demonstration of strength, dexterity, and courage always attract many students. In particular, in order to implement the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 25, 2022 “On measures to popularize and develop types of ethnosports” and the large-scale celebration of the national holiday Navruz in the Branch, national sports competitions were organized within the territory of the students’ residence hall, in during which students competed in such national sports as national wrestling, tug of war, archery and other sports arts.

Undoubtedly, at the Branch each of the students, according to their interests, can choose how to spend their leisure time, in the sports section, or by participating in the performance of a student team or Student Scientific Union. And if a student has the talent to play on stage, he can play a certain musical instrument, plays music or has good vocal abilities, then the doors of the Rendezvous theater studio, created on the initiative of students in 2017, are always open. The main principle of the studio theater is teamwork and personal participation of everyone in the common cause, and the participants of “Rendezvous” always delight the audience with their productions dedicated to holidays or significant events.

A qualitatively new form of organizing meaningful leisure time for students has become the activity of the volunteer movement “Student Volunteer Initiative”, which main goal is to expand opportunities for self-realization for everyone and enhance the role of volunteering in public life. The volunteer movement is represented by various sectors, such as “Healthy Generation”, “Social Assistance”, “Media of the Day”, “Green Zone” and “Academic Environment”.

Despite the fact that the Branch’s volunteer movement is relatively young, it already numbers more than a hundred students. In particular, on the eve of the New Year, on the initiative of volunteers from the Social Assistance sector, an annual charity trip was organized to boarding school № 125 for children with disabilities, which is located in Gazalkent in Tashkent region. In addition, in February-March, the volunteer movement organized charity fairs, which revenues were spent on a charitable visit to the “Sakhovat” nursing home. Holding such events is clear evidence that the volunteer movement is actively implementing various creative ideas and projects, laying the foundation for a good tradition of implementing volunteer initiatives.

Moreover, volunteers of the Green Zone sector participated in an event held on the eve of the Navruz holiday, when more than 700 seedlings were planted on the adjacent territory of the sponsored academic lyceum within the framework of the “Yashil Makon” (“Green Area”) project by students of the Branch, students of the sponsored lyceum and the faculty. This campaign was held in accordance with the implementation of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 30, 2021 №PD-46 “On measures to accelerate the planting of trees in

the republic, more effective organization of tree protection.” Undoubtedly, the trees planted by the students of the Gubkin University will improve the landscape and make a significant contribution to ensuring the sustainability of ecosystems in our environment.

All activities implemented at the Branch are aimed not only at training highly qualified personnel for the oil and gas industry of our republic, but also at unlocking the intellectual and creative potential of future specialists, enhancing their responsibility and involvement in ongoing large-scale reforms.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №60 “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” dated January 28, 2022.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №-6309 “On further support for gifted youth studying and engaged in research activities in higher educational institutions of the republic” dated September 9, 2021.
3. Hojiyev R. B., Xolmosminov G.B., Sharipov M.L. Raising a Harmoniously Developed Generation is a Priority of Democratic Reforms in Uzbekistan // European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 2020. № 8 (5). p. 1-3.